

PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST THE ACCUMULATION OF RAILCARS ON SIDING TRACKS DURING CUSTOMER SERVICE OPERATIONS

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Abstract. *A mathematical model has been developed to optimize the implementation of technological processes for delivering goods in the article. This mathematical model enables separate optimization of delivery methods for goods. Additionally, in the article, the optimization of the dispatch time of wagons from the station and the influence of the execution interval when removing wagons from the cargo front have been assessed. The proposed mathematical model aims to create the possibility of accurately allocating the intervals of operations performed during the dispatch of goods from the station by modeling, thereby optimizing the process of dispatching wagons from the station and efficiently managing the retention of wagons in the cargo front during the delivery of goods. In the proposed technology, the determination of the delivery time for a specific type of cargo presented for transportation is possible by establishing coefficients that take various factors into account, based on illustrative information for the upcoming period. This allows for the estimation of the distance covered by a wagon in terms of its daily capacity.*

Keywords: *wagon, wagon shipment, delivery time, shunting operations, technological operations.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The effective execution of a shipping contract established within the railway transportation sector plays a significant role in contributing to the national economy by ensuring high quality and timely transportation services. In providing transportation services, one of the primary requirements set by the shipper and the recipient in railway transportation is the timely delivery of goods to the specified destination.

Timely execution of delivery deadlines is considered one of the most crucial issues for any transportation. Railway transportation occupies a significant position in economic development. The main direction to ensure competitiveness and sustainable development in railway transportation involves meeting customers' demands, fostering competition, and balancing clients' and service providers' interests. At present, specific demands are placed on transportation services, especially in cargo transportation. The high-level accomplishment of delivering goods within the specified timeframe is crucial [1,3].

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Additional rates for services and operations related to the transportation of cargo, passengers, baggage, and cargo baggage are established on a contractual basis.

Optimizing the operation works on railway transportation, developing a theory for evaluating the delivery time of goods during the transportation process, involving prominent international experts, and [4]:

K.P. Shenfeld [6] proposed transitioning to the method of determining the delivery time for transporting goods, taking into account the technology of the transportation process and considering the type of cargo. Additionally, mathematical statistics methods are suggested for determining the delivery time by considering the characteristics of technological processes in the transportation process. These mathematical statistics will lead to changes in the standards for the delivery of goods after the increase in the ability to transfer trains in the future.

There is a need to organize the following information to assess the methodology recommended for optimizing the expedited delivery of goods:

- Conducting a thorough analysis of shipments based on participants involved in the speedy delivery of goods;
- Developing a comprehensive technology chain for operations carried out on the railway during the expedited delivery of goods;
- Enhancing confidence in calculating tariff distances and additional services for expeditious delivery [5,6].

Generally, groupage freight trains are widely used for transporting goods on the United Kingdom and France railways. In organizing such groupage freight trains, the grouping of wagons is strategically arranged based on the destinations of groups within the train composition to avoid the need to rearrange wagons at technical stations along the route. The transport service policy of the French railways is designed to meet the demands of freight shippers. Freight trains with wagons weighing 400 to 800 tons, designated to complete delivery within the deadlines agreed upon with freight shippers, move at speeds of up to 110 km/h along approved routes without reprocessing at technical stations along the railway. Customers who use railway services have complained about the shortcomings in delivering goods on time within the “Uzbekiston temir yullari” joint-stock company [8].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The analytical review within the “Uzbekiston temir yullari” joint-stock company indicates that the speed of delivering local goods by rail ranges from 70 to 225 km per day. The recent analyses suggest a decline in these indicators in recent years [5].

1-schedule

The main reasons for freight not reaching its destination within the specified timeframe and for leaving wagons stationed at stations are:

The technological processes of delivery The main technological processes that are carried out	The time required for movement on the section	The time spent by the wagons awaiting reprocessing at the station	The time spent by the wagons that are not undergoing reprocessing while stationed at the station	The time for dispatching wagons from the station	The time for receiving wagons at the station
	Amount of exposure				
	13 %	48 %	13 %	18 %	8 %
Waiting and standing of wagons at freight and intermediate stations on railway sections	+	+	+	+	+
Unavailability of electric locomotives at railway stations	-	+	-	+	+
Insufficiency of train locomotives on railway sections	+	-	+	-	-
The wagons remain stationed at sorting stations until further processing.	-	+	-	-	-
Wagons waiting in the assembly yard for the formation of a train composition	-	+	-	+	+
Waiting for the dispatch of	-	+	-	-	-

assembled trains from the station					
Temporary waiting of locomotives at stations during the movement of trains and other factors	-	-	+	-	-

In modern conditions, greater attention is being paid to addressing issues related to the timely delivery of goods in railway transportation through the implementation of relevant monitoring technologies. However, the breakdown of technological processes in implementing these measures may hinder achieving the expected results in fulfilling delivery deadlines. In this way, identifying the main reasons for delays in the transportation of goods by rail, determining the method of specifying delivery deadlines, and developing measures to eliminate them are aimed at improving them through the refinement of monitoring technologies and optimization of the transportation process.

Developing a mathematical model for the grouped shipment type of goods.

It considers the time spent on mechanized and non-mechanized methods in loading and unloading goods, encompassing preparation, assisting, and completion operations. The operations of preparing groups of wagons for loading or unloading, excluding operations with all wagons except the first and processes with other wagons excluding the last, are not considered when calculating the time for loading or unloading groups of wagons. t_j - the time required for dispatching wagons from the station per day. (Regulations for Freight Transportation on the Railway Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan). The following processes must be organized when sending wagons taken from the freight yard to the station. Ensuring the loading and unloading of wagons during the dispatch from the station and regulating the sending and receiving interval within an hour is emphasized. In guaranteeing this interval, we should consider the performance of locomotive services, loading and unloading mechanisms, and ongoing operations. Similarly, the execution interval for loading and unloading wagons at the freight yard during intake and release is related to the operational process involving scheduled and grouped wagons.

The process of rearranging the wagons to the front is carried out as follows:

$$I = \frac{m t_{load}}{m_{wagon}} + t_{deliv.} + t_{t.out.}, \text{ hours} \quad (3)$$

With the rearrangement of the wagons:

$$I' = \frac{mt_{load}}{m_{wagon}} + \left(\frac{m}{m_{wagon}} - 1\right)t_{rear.} + t_{deliv.} + t_{t.out}, \text{ hours} \quad (4)$$

Bu yerda:

m - the number of grouped or routed wagons, hours;

t_{load} - the time to load or unload the goods on a single wagon, hours;

m_{wagon} - the number of wagons loaded or unloaded at a given time;

$t_{rear.}$ - the time for rearrangement, hours;

$t_{deliv.}$ - the time for delivering wagons to the front, hours;

$t_{t.out}$ - the time for taking wagons out from the front, hours;

The time interval for taking wagons out and delivering them to the branch roads, as well as placing grouped or routed wagons during loading and unloading, is determined as follows:

Without rearranging the wagons:

$$I_h = \frac{mt_{load}}{m_{wagon}} + \frac{m}{m_{placed}} (t_{deliv.} + t_{t.out} + t_{depar.}) \quad (5)$$

With the rearrangement of the wagons:

$$I'_h = \frac{mt_{load}}{m_{wagon}} + \left(\frac{m}{m_{wagon}} - \frac{m}{m_{placed}}\right)t_{rear.} + \frac{m}{m_{placed}} (t_{deliv.} + t_{t.out} + t_{depar.}) \quad (6)$$

m_{placed} - the number of wagons that can be placed at the loading area at a given time;

$t_{depar.}$ - the departure time of the locomotive with a specific route or wagons from the station, hours.

The concerned party should provide information about the time of taking wagons in and out within the day. The appointment of a responsible person for receiving and accepting information is a condition. If the branch road owner is taken in or out by a diesel locomotive, the maintenance time is calculated from when it was received or delivered on the rail track. The faster the travel time from the sending station to the designated station, the quicker the utilization of the wagons. The movement of wagons along the railway without undergoing additional processing positively affects the delivery time of cargo [4].

3. RESULTS

The time of taking the wagons in and out must be notified within a day. The appointment of a responsible person is required for receiving and accepting the message by the company. Suppose the wagons are taken in or taken out by the branch road's maneuvering locomotive owner. In that case, the time is calculated from when the railway has received or delivered the wagons.

In this case, you can see the results of the MatLab program in the route, group withdrawal of wagons from the freight front, and interaction with incoming wagons.

Figure 3. Change in the time interval during the removal of wagons at the cargo front

During cargo dispatch in the routed shipment type, the complete composition is assembled either on the branch road or in the freight yards and then sent to the destination station. Since the cargo line is single, the sender dispatches the cargo as a single train [5].

4. CONCLUSION

The research results indicated that, in the process of dispatching wagons at the station, there has been no consideration given to separate accounting for types of dispatching in the context of loading from the freight front and removing wagons, following the Regulations on Cargo Transportation by Rail in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this article, the impact of taking wagons from the freight front when dispatching cargoes from the station to different types of dispatching has been emphasized, and mathematical models have been developed. Considering the performance indicators highlighted in the article for dispatching loaded wagons from the station allows for expedited cargo delivery. Furthermore, in this article, the optimization of dispatching wagons from the station is discussed regarding the cargo dispatch type and the mutual influence on processing intervals when taking wagons from the freight front.

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